

The BioTrack Project

Development of a protocol for biometric-based animal tracking and tracing

Review of biometric and electronic systems of livestock identification

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1. Introduction

Recent animal health and foodborne illness scares in all parts of the world are creating a demand for source verification, food safety and supply chain identification of meat products. The increasing awareness of food-related safety issues among today's food consumers, along with a more educated public, is driving the demand for more information about the vertical food supply chain. The International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) defines "traceability" as "the ability to trace the history, application or location of what is under consideration". Within the context of livestock, traceability refers to the ability to identify farm animals and their products (especially their meat) according to their origin, as far in the production sequence as is necessary. A key prerequisite for effective traceability is a system of unique and secure identification based on tamper-proof identifiers.

However, the traditional livestock identification systems (ranging from plastic ear tags to hot brands and tattoos) have proven to be amenable to loss, damage and possible fraudulent operations as well as being object of recent animal welfare concerns. With the advent of the biometrics technology, new types of livestock identifiers have been proposed (retinal and iris imaging, muzzle pattern, DNA fingerprint and immunological labelling). By definition, a biometric labelling system is permanent, cannot be easily faked, altered or appropriated, and therefore it is less prone to error and fraud. In this context, the BioTrack project (Ward, 2005) aims to investigate (i) on the embracement of biometric identifiers for tamper-proof animal identification, and (ii) on suitable electronic tagging systems that enable the biometric to be stored on the animal.

This review presents (i) a brief description of the main biometric technologies for human identification, (ii) a discussion of the main driving forces for livestock identification and their importance, (iii) the advantages and drawbacks of the traditional animal identifiers and the electronic RFID-based tags, (iv) a detailed description of the latest developments on biometric-based animal identifiers, and (v) a summary of research opportunities on livestock biometrics within the BioTrack project.

2. Biometrics in Humans

Biometrics is the technique of identifying people based on their distinctive anatomical (e.g., face, fingerprint, iris, retina, hand geometry) and behavioural (e.g., signature, gait) characteristics (Jain *et al.*, 2004). Biometrics originated from the need of effectively identifying people since biometric identifiers cannot be shared or misplaced, and they intrinsically represent the individual's bodily identity. Virtually, any physiological feature could be used for identification.

Biometrics broadly provides the following three functionalities (Jain *et al.*, 2004):

- Positive identification,
- Large scale identification, and
- Screening

2.1 Positive identification

Biometrics can verify with high certainty the authenticity of a claimed enrolment based on the input biometric sample. Commercial applications such as computer network logon, electronic data security, ATMs, credit card purchases, physical access control, cellular phones and medical records management are sample authentication applications. Authentication applications are typically cost sensitive with a strong incentive for being user-friendly.

2.2 Large scale identification

Given an input biometric sample, a large-scale identification determines if the pattern is associated with any of a large number of enrolled identities. Typical large-scale identification applications include welfare-disbursement, national ID cards, border control, voter ID cards, driver's license, criminal investigation, corpse identification, parenthood determination, etc. These large-scale identification applications require a large sustainable throughput with as little human supervision as possible.

2.3 Screening

Screening applications determine whether a person belongs to a watch-list of identities. Examples of screening applications could include airport security, security at public events, and other surveillance applications. By their nature, the screening applications (i) do not have a well-defined “user” enrolment phase; (ii) can expect only minimal control over their subjects and imaging conditions; and (iii) require large sustainable throughput with as little human supervision as possible. Neither large-scale identification nor screening can be accomplished without biometrics (e.g., by using token-based or knowledge-based identification).

3. Biometric Identification

Biometric identification systems typically follow three high-level processing steps (Figure 1). First, the system must acquire an image of the attribute through an appropriate scanning technique. Once the scanned content is acquired, it must be localised for processing purposes. During this step, extraneous informational content is discarded and minutiae are isolated and turned into a template, a sort of internal canonical form for matching attributes stored in a database. Finally, templates stored in the database are searched for a match with the one just presented. If a match is found, the identification is a success.

Figure 1. Biometric identification process

3.1 Accuracy of biometric systems

Almost a century after the fingerprints were observed to be distinctive, a 2004 fingerprint contest (FVC, 2004) revealed that fingerprint matching algorithms may have false non-match error rate of 2%. Similarly, even though the first paper on automatic face recognition appeared in the early 70's, the state-of-the-art face recognition systems are known to be fragile according to recent operational tests (Phillips *et al.*, 2002).

Jain *et al.* (2004) explained that the complexity of designing a biometric system is based on three main factors: accuracy, scale or size of database, and usability. The grand challenge is to design a biometric system that is easy to use, that can be applied to a large database and yet works with high accuracy.

3.1.1 Accuracy

Unlike password or token-based systems, a practical biometric system does not make perfect match decisions and can make two basic types of errors (Jain *et al.*, 2004):

- (i) False match: the biometric system incorrectly declares a successful match between the input pattern and a non-matching pattern in the database.
- (ii) False non-match: the biometric system incorrectly declares failure of match between the input pattern and a matching pattern in the database.

There are three primary reasons underlying imperfect accuracy performance of a biometric system (Jain *et al.*, 2004):

- (i) Information limitation: The invariant and distinctive information content in the pattern samples may be inherently limited due to the intrinsic signal capacity. For instance, the distinctive information in

hand geometry is less than in fingerprints. Consequently hand geometry can differentiate fewer identities than the fingerprint signal. Information limitation may also be due to poorly controlled biometric presentation by the users or inconsistent signal acquisition.

- (ii) Representation limitation: The ideal representation scheme should be designed to retain all invariance and discriminatory information in the sensed measurements. Practical feature extraction systems, typically based on simplistic models of biometric signal, fail to capture the richness of information in a realistic biometric signal resulting in the inclusion of erroneous features and exclusion of true features. Figure 2 illustrates typical “poor quality” prints that cannot be processed by traditional minutiae-based fingerprint identification system.

Figure 2. Examples of “poor quality” fingerprints

- (iii) Invariance limitation: Given a representation scheme, the design of an ideal matcher should perfectly model the invariance relationship in different patterns from the same class, even when imaged under different presentation conditions.

The design challenge is to be able to arrive at a realistic representational / invariance model of the identifier from a few samples acquired under inconsistent conditions, and then, formally estimate the discriminatory information in the signal from the samples.

3.1.2 Scale

The number of identities in the enrolled database affects the speed and accuracy of the system. In the case of verification systems, the size of the database does not really matter since it essentially involves a 1:1 match, comparing one set of submitted samples to one set of enrolment records. In the case of large scale identification and screening systems containing a total of N identities, sequentially performing N 1:1 matches is not effective. Thus, there is a need for efficiently scaling the system to control throughput and false-match error rates with an increase in the size of the database.

Typical approaches to scaling include using multiple hardware units, coarse pattern classification (e.g., first classifying a fingerprint into major classes such as Arch, Tented Arch, Whorl, Left Loop and Right Loop) and extensive use of “exogenous” data (e.g., gender, age, geographical location) supplied by human operators.

3.2 Biometric technologies

The heightened awareness of security issues has led to a massive rise in the interest for biometric technology from a variety of market sectors. In 2004, the traditional market segments for biometrics were law enforcement, government sector, financial sector, health care and travel and transportation.

Industry predictions indicate that the total biometrics market will continue to grow, reaching by 2008 \$4600 million revenues (Figure 3). With regard to the different biometric technologies in use, fingerprint continues to be the leading technology in terms of market share (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Total biometrics revenue market: 2003 – 2008 (including AFIS revenue). Extracted from “Biometrics Market and Industry Report 2004-2008”

Figure 4. Biometric market share by technology in 2004. Extracted from “Biometrics Market and Industry Report 2004-2008”

3.2.1 Fingerprint

Fingerprint identification is probably the best-known biometric technique, because of its widespread application in forensic sciences and law enforcement scenarios. It was in 1893 when the Home Ministry Office, UK, accepted that no two individuals have the same fingerprints and set in motion a chain of events that led to the first Automatic Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS) in the 1960s. The use of AFIS as an effective tool for criminal investigation and background checks is prevalent worldwide. The AFIS system at FBI consists of a large database of approximately 46 million “ten prints” and conducts, on average, approximately 50 000 searches per day (Jain *et al.*, 2004).

Fingerprints have a pattern composed of ridges and valleys that is unique to each individual and keeps stable along the entire life. For fingerprint identification, data acquisition is carried out by placing the finger over a scanning device. The most popular technology to obtain a live-scan fingerprint is based on optical frustrated total internal reflection (FTIR) concept. Other live-scan imaging methods are based on ultrasound total internal reflection, sensing of differential capacitance, noncontact 3D scanning, etc.

3.2.2 Hand geometry

This biometric technique is based on the fact that virtually every person’s hand is uniquely shaped, and this shape does not significantly change after a certain age. Although it is not the most reliable, hand biometric is inexpensive and easily acceptable to users (Table 1). The essence of hand geometry is the comparative dimensions of fingers and the location of joints. One of the earliest automated biometric systems, Indentimat, during the late 60s used hand geometry and stayed in production for almost twenty years. Some systems perform simple, two-dimensional measurements of the palm of the hand. Others attempt to construct a simple three-dimensional image from which to extract template characteristics.

Table 1. Characteristics of the most important human biometric technologies. Extracted from de Luis-García *et al.* (2003)

Biometric type	Accuracy	Ease of use	User acceptance	Ease of implementation	Cost
Fingerprint	High	Medium	Low	High	Medium
Hand geometry	Medium	High	Medium	Medium	High
Voice	Medium	High	High	High	Low
Retina	High	Low	Low	Low	Medium
Iris	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	High
Signature	Medium	Medium	High	Low	Medium
Face	Low	High	High	Medium	Low

3.2.3 Iris

Human iris is an extremely valuable source of biometric information, as it is a very complex structure unique to an individual. The visual appearance of the iris is a result of its layered structure being the general structure genetically determined. However, the particular details are critically dependent on circumstances as the initial conditions in the embryonic precursor to the iris. Thus, two different irises are extremely unlikely to be equal, even in the case of genetically identical twins or clones (Daugman *et al.*, 2001).

Iris scanning is less intrusive than retinal recognition because the iris is easily visible from several feet away. Responses of the iris to changes in light can provide secondary verification that the iris presented as a biometric factor is genuine. While the iris seems to be consistent throughout adulthood, it does vary somewhat up to adolescence.

Data collection is critical in iris recognition systems since it is not easy to obtain a valid image of such a small region with limited user cooperation. If the user will only be asked to stand in front of the system, artificial vision

techniques such as the use of stereo cameras may be used to first locate the position of the eye and then capture an image of the region of interest by means of a CCD camera. The complexity can be reduced if the user is asked to place his eye in front of the camera. In this case, some feedback will be needed to help the user to position appropriately (de Luis-García *et al.*, 2003).

Several iris recognition systems have been developed (Table 2, Figure 5), which exploit the complexity and stability over time of iris patterns and claim to be highly accurate. Most recent approaches include the ones developed by Sanchez and Sanchez (2005), Ganeshan *et al.* (2005), and Yu *et al.* (2005).

Figure 5. Example of an iris pattern, imaged monochromatically. The outline overlay shows results of the iris and pupil localization and eyelid detection steps. The bit stream in the top left is the result of demodulation with complex-valued 2D Gabor wavelets to encode the phase sequence of the iris pattern
Extracted from Daugman (1993)

3.2.4 Retinal scan

Retinal recognition creates an “eye signature” from the vascular configuration situated at the back of the eye. Although, it is an extremely consistent and reliable attribute with the advantage of being protected inside the eye itself, its being intrusive is a major drawback for this kind of biometric technique (de Luis-García *et al.*, 2003). An image of the retina is captured by having the individual look through a lens at an alignment target. The pattern is analysed for characteristic points which form the discriminant information. Diseases or

Table 2. A list of several approaches for iris identification in humans

Stages	Brief explanation	Reference
Pre-processing	Application of pseudo polar coordinates and standardising the radial size of the iris (Figure 5)	Daugman (1993)
	Iris contours are determined by edge detectors applied along predetermined paths based on Hough transforms.	Wildes (1997)
	Iris region is located and mapped into a rectangular image of fixed size.	Lim <i>et al.</i> (2001)
Feature extraction	2D Gabor wavelets are used to perform a multiscale analysis of the iris. A set of quadrature pair frequency-selective filters are used to analyse regions of the image at different scales. These filters obtain information about local phase, which is coded with two bits attending the sign of the real and imaginary parts. 2048 phase bits are obtained to form a 256-byte code, which represents each iris and is called IrisCode (Figure 5).	Daugman (1993) Daugman (1988) Daugman (1985)
	Feature extraction is based on an isotropic bandpass decomposition derived from the application of Laplacian to Gaussian filters to the image data	Wildes (1997)
	After normalisation of the iris diameter, concentric circles are drawn and one-dimensional signals are obtained from the corresponding section. These circular sections are then analysed using a dyadic wavelet transform from which a zero-crossing representation is generated next.	Boles and Boashash (1998)
	Feature extraction is performed using Haar wavelets, which are applied four times in order to obtain several sub-images. The feature vector is composed of 84 features from the sub-image of the high-pass filter of the fourth transform and each average value from the three remaining high-pass filter sub-images. In this way, the dimension of the resulting vector is 87, each value is quantized into a binary image so that the iris image is finally represented by 87 bits.	Lim <i>et al.</i> (2001)
Matching algorithm	The norm of the resultant bit vector is normalised in order to compute a hamming distance where 0 would represent a perfect match.	Daugman (1993)
	Based on Fisher's linear discrimination applying a threshold afterwards.	Wildes (1997)
	Based on two different similarity functions that compare the zero-crossing representations.	Boles and Boashash (1998)
	Matching and decision stages are performed using a LVQ neural network which, after a training phase, compares two representations and decides whether they correspond to the same or different irises.	Lim <i>et al.</i> (2001)

Table 3. Eye-based biometric technology industries in the market. Compiled from Anonymous (2003; 2005a)

Biometrics	Companies	Remarks
Iris	Iridian Technologies (US)	Original patents for iris recognition and matching algorithms (“Iris Recognition System” U.S. Patent No. 4641349, Flom, L., and Safir, A., issued in 1987) cover 16 countries and does not expire internationally until 2006.
	IrisGuard (UK)	"Biometric Personal Identification System Based on Iris Analysis” U.S. Patent No. 5291560 issued in 1994 (J. Daugman).
	Senex Technologies (South Korea)	Launched a device called TrueEYE, which uses an alternative iris acquisition and processing algorithms to Iridian’s technology.
	IriTech (South Korea)	The matching algorithm developed by IriTech is claimed to address many of the difficulties caused by poor input images that can arise in various adverse conditions.
	Alpha Engineering, Evermedia (South Korea)	
Retina	Retinal Technologies (US)	Working on a device that will overcome many of the drawbacks to earlier designs of the technology (size, cost and intrusiveness)
	EyeDentify (Belgium)	Producing an enhanced version of the EyeDentify ICAM 2001 device.
	ACM Biometric Security Engineering Department (Italy)	– Work is being done on acquiring cow’s and racehorse’s retinas for livestock applications using a 25x optical system in combination with infrared light and a pocket PC.

injuries that would interfere with the retina are comparatively rare, so the attribute normally remains both consistent and consistently available.

3.2.5 Voice

Voice recognition techniques are generally categorised according to two approaches: Automatic Speaker Verification (ASV) and Automatic Speaker Identification (ASI). Speaker verification uses voice as the authenticating attribute. Speaker identification attempts to use voice to identify who an individual actually is. Voice recognition distinguishes an individual by matching particular voice traits against templates stored in a database. Feature extraction normally measures formants or sound characteristics unique to each person's vocal tract.

Speaker verification technologies are divided into two major categories (de Luis-García *et al.*, 2003):

- (i) Text-dependent applications, where the system associates a sentence, possibly different, to each client. One particular case of text-dependent speaker verification is known as *text prompted*, where the system *prompts* the potential client with a sentence, which could be different for each access.
- (ii) Text-independent applications, where the client is not requested to say the same sentence during each access. Thus, the only information used by the system is the acoustic characteristics of the client.

3.2.6 Face recognition

Face recognition is probably the most user-friendly biometric technology, but it is still at its early stages, and most tests and applications have been run against relatively small databases. The similarity score produced by each comparison determines the match. A facial thermogram is similar to face recognition except that the image is captured by an infrared camera, and the

heat signature of the face is used to create the biometric template used for matching. This is more reliable than simple imaging.

3.2.7 Hand vein

Hand vein recognition attempts to distinguish individuals by measuring the differences in subcutaneous features of the hand using infrared imaging. Like face recognition, it must deal with the extra issues of three-dimensional space and the orientation of the hand. Like retinal scanning, it relies on the pattern of the veins in the hand to build a template with which to attempt matches against templates stored in a database. The use of infrared imaging offers some of the same advantages as hand geometry over fingerprint recognition in manufacturing or shop-floor applications where hands may not be clean enough to scan properly using a conventional video or capacitance technique.

3.2.8 Signature

This biometric has a long history and has a wide current usage in document authentication and transaction authorisation. Forensic experts have developed criteria over the years for verifying the authenticity of a signature. Offline recognition requires that signatures are scanned from paper documents and then analysed, whereas online recognition (Nalwa, 1997) uses devices that capture the dynamic information as the signature is being written. In addition to the general shape of the signed name, a signature recognition system can also measure both the pressure and velocity of the point of the stylus across the sensor pad. Signatures, however, are difficult to model for variation.

Other biometric identification technologies include keystroke dynamics, palm-print features and ear recognition.

4. Traceability of livestock

The ISO 8402 standard defines traceability as “the capacity for establishing a product’s origin, process history, use and provenance by reference to written records”.

In a report on traceability, Golan *et al.* (2004) defined three key parameters that can be used to characterise traceability systems:

- **breadth** of a system: the amount of information recorded, such as vaccination, feed regime, etc;
- **depth** of a system: how far back or forward the system tracks. In many cases, the depth of a system is determined by its breadth or attributes of interest; and
- **precision**: the degree of assurance with which the tracing system can pinpoint the movement of a particular product, and is described with reference to an acceptable error rate, or what would happen if there were mistaken in tracking the product.

Tracing the source of livestock has become more complicated in recent years. Many livestock, notably cattle and sheep, are now traded many times before being ready for slaughter. Animals can be slaughtered hundreds of kilometres from the original place of rearing, and in Europe, international trade of live food animals is particularly common (Pettitt, 2001). The increased risk of epidemic spread of diseases caused by the freedom of livestock movement is acknowledged and highlighted in Council Resolution 94/C 16/01. The resolution reaffirms the role and responsibilities of official services and advocates the research of appropriate means to ensure efficient surveillance of farming concerns from a veterinary point of view, with the intention of guaranteeing health standards (McGrann and Wiseman, 2001).

A prerequisite for effective traceability is a system of unique and secure identification based on tamper proof identifiers linked directly to a database. Such a database must be capable of supporting animal identification, health records and traceability to the holding of origin. This information needs to be securely transferred between national

databases and be accessible immediately (McGrann and Wiseman, 2001; Wismans, 1999).

4.1 Animal identification and verification

Animal secure identification and fraud-proof source verification are needed for (Smith *et al.*, 2005; Golan, 2004; Shadduck and Golden, 2002a; Marchant, 2002):

- protection of property from theft or loss by livestock owners,
- efficient control or eradication of animal diseases,
- supporting business to business transactions involving livestock,
- preventing fraud in animal subsidy programs,
- assuring food safety and high quality brand name retail meat products,
- enabling efficient trace back systems for food-borne diseases,
- promoting consumer confidence – to assure market access in global trade and to deliver on brand promise via added assurances and authenticity management,
- adding value as a benefit of supply-chain management – preservation of intended value traits created by use of genetics, origin of production, unique inputs or processing method.

4.1.1 Animal health

The need to trace the origin of animals arises as soon as control programmes for infectious disease are implemented in a population. The existence of an identification and registration system for animals and animal holdings is often crucial for planning and implementing actions for prevention and control of diseases (Caporale *et al.*, 2001). For instance, cattle identification has played an important role in the health and viability of the livestock in Canada. From the 50s to the 80s, parallel efforts were mounted to eradicate brucellosis, and approximately 95% of the cow herd in Canada was individually identified under the Health of Animals programme. In 1985, Canada was declared free of brucellosis (Stanford *et al.*, 2001).

International trade has increased concerns about the movement of animal diseases across borders. One of the main missions of the OIE (Office International des Epizooties) is to guarantee the sanitary safety of world trade by developing rules for international trade in animals and animal products. OIE standards for animal health and animal diseases that are transmissible to humans are recognised by the World Trade Organisation (WTO) as reference international sanitary rules (Marchant, 2002).

4.1.2 Consumer protection

An animal identification system will impact on consumer protection as:

- it enhances disease control and eradication capabilities for rapid containment of foreign animal disease outbreaks and enhanced ability to respond to biosecurity threats;
- it enables industry to meet foreign and domestic consumer demands for source-verified products; and
- it mitigates intentional and unintentional biosecurity threats to the food supply.

4.1.3 Food safety

A link between the animal producer and the slaughter / processing industries through the use of animal identification will certainly ensure food safety. A traceback and recall system from final sale to producer for animals and products destined to the human food supply would generate data that is important to the prevention of disease in humans and would enable processors to recognise potential hazards in the food chain (Vitiello and Thaler, 2001).

In food safety policies based on “hazard analysis and critical control point”, producers are asked to guarantee the quality of animal products by documenting that all steps of the food chain, from feed safety and animal health status, to final product wholesomeness, are clearly known and under control so that appropriate corrective actions can be taken if required. A

hazard analysis of processing steps from the farm to the point at which animals are presented for slaughter, and subsequently into processing and retail would enable public health officials to take informed steps to protect the public from pathogens, diseases or violative residues.

In addition, a reliable animal identification system would enable public health officials to trace forward to prevent consumption of animal products that are found to have been exposed to latent diseases or harmful pathogens. Hathaway and McKenzie (1991) suggest that information and data requirements may extend beyond the slaughterhouse to the consumer or back to the farm and port of origin. For instance, the health status of herds and flocks could be determined in advance of transportation to slaughter so that high-risk animals could be separated from low-risk animals for the purposes of both slaughter and inspection. These data, in combination with pathogen baseline data and microbiological profiles of products could help identify farm management and animal marketing practices that affect food safety.

Smith *et al.* (2000) discussed traceback capabilities as being important relative to food safety because (a) product traceability would help minimise potential danger of meatborne pathogens to the restaurant industry, (b) traceback to the birth of the animal would be beneficial in reducing the threat of meatborne pathogen occurrence in the meat purveying sector, and (d) consumer groups would like to start to build a better database on traceback and assure that recall authority and traceback (relative to food poisoning organisms) are under government authority.

4.1.4 Cost distribution

Animal identification that allows traceback throughout the farm-to-table continuum would allow the cost of food-borne illness and the benefits from preventive measures to be attributed to the appropriate segments of the food chain (Vitiello and Thaler, 2001). In this way, farmers who can prove through traceability documentation, that their animals are more valuable (due to up-to-date vaccination, proper medical care, animal welfare provisions, etc.) are

more likely to be able to negotiate higher prices for their animals (Golan, 2004).

The need for a national livestock identification system is based, in part, on private need to assist producers in maximising the profit of their agricultural enterprise and assuring its sustainability by identifying those animals that consistently grow as quickly as possible, eat the least amount of feed, require the least amount of medical treatment, produce the best grading carcass, etc (Smith *et al.*, 2005).

4.2 Traditional animal identifiers

4.2.1 Ear notching

Ear notching is widely used in the US swine industry as a system of animal identification (Neary and Yager, 2002). It involves removing V-shaped portions of the pig's ear that correspond to a specific litter number and also an individual pig number from that litter. There are many systems of ear notching, but when using the system of ear notching required by the purebred swine association of the US, the litter number is notched in the pig's right ear, and the individual pig number is notched in the pig's left ear (Figure 6). A disadvantage of this method is the bleed and discomfort caused to the pigs.

4.2.2 Plastic and bar-coded ear tags

Ear tags are another common form of identification used in all species. The tags are pierced through the animal's ear, and allow for an animal to be identified from the front and the back. Tags are normally installed between the second and third cartilage rib of one or both ears, using an applicator gun that corresponds to the type of ear tag being used. Ear tags are easy to use, flexible in all types of weather, inexpensive and usually easy to read. The main drawbacks of ear tags are that they can be easily ripped from the ear or

become lost, their possibility of tearing injuries, and potential fraudulent identification.

Figure 6. Ear notching system used by the purebred swine associations of the United States

4.2.3 Freeze branding

This method allows for animals to be identified from a greater distance than with ear tags. Freeze branding involves the use of branding irons, with letters and numbers, being chilled in liquid nitrogen or dry ice and alcohol. Upon application to the animal's hide, the chilled branding iron kills the cells that produce colour pigment in the hair follicles. After freeze branding, white or colourless follicles are produced in the branded region, which results in permanent brand. Disadvantages of freeze branding include the permanency of this method and the fact that a brand can never be removed or replaced as well as aesthetic concerns.

4.2.4 Tattooing

Tattooing is commonly used in all species and involves imprinting an identification number / letter combination into the skin of the animal using indelible ink. Normally, for cattle, goats, sheep and swine, the tattoo is placed above the first rib of the ear so it does not interfere with the use of ear tags. Horses are often tattooed on the inside of their flank, and swine can be

tattooed on the shoulder for carcass identification during slaughter. One disadvantage of tattooing is that the animal must be restrained to apply and read the identification number (Neary and Yager, 2002).

4.2.5 Muzzle printing

Muzzle patterns of cattle are uneven features of their skin surface. Nose printing is useful because it cannot be modified in any way. It is used as a form of permanent identification, and is most commonly used for the sale and exhibition of sheep and cattle. In Japan, it has been used in registration of beef cattle for breeding and marketing (Figure 7). More than 3 million beef cattle have been registered at Wagyu Registry Association in Kyoto since 1948 (Minagawa *et al.*, 2002). Printing is performed by restraining the animal's head, either in a head gate or with a halter, and placing a minimal amount of ink on the animal's dried nose. The ink is then transferred to an index card, supported by a wooden block or stiff backing, by pressing the card against the animal's nose. Problems associated with nose printing include: the use of too much ink, a build-up of moisture on the animal's nose, and not holding the animal still, can result in a smeared, unreadable print (Neary and Yager, 2002).

Figure 7. Examples of muzzle patterns of an animal at the age of 2 months (left) and at the age of 14 months (right). Extracted from Minagawa *et al.* (2002)

Although this method of identification has proven to be accurate, its main disadvantage is the length of time to take the print and the difficulty in obtaining it. Fitzgerald (2004) reported that the time to obtain a muzzle printing per animal could reach up to 6 minutes.

4.3 Electronic identifiers

All three types of electronic devices (ear tags, ruminal boluses and injectable transponders) were evaluated in a four-year project (1998-2001) in six European countries (France, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands, Portugal and Spain) to gather information on the feasibility of introducing an electronic animal identification system in the EU. This EU study was conducted because the current tracking system relied on manual and visible inspection of ear tags and tattoos. Outbreaks of livestock diseases within the EU, such as Foot and Mouth and BSE, demonstrated that the livestock identification systems used did not provide reliable and efficient disease monitoring and traceability. The general conclusions and results from the IDEA project were quite positive. It was concluded that implementing an electronic identification system is feasible. It also demonstrated that transponder technology used for electronic identification would substantially improve the current livestock identification, registration and management system in the EU (see 4.3.4).

There are several requirements for the place of application of a transponder (Artmann *et al.*, 1999): (i) it must be attached to the animal in such a manner that it cannot be lost or mechanically destroyed, (2) stress to the animal must remain as minimal as possible, (3) the location of the transponder may not change after application, (4) the application location must be readily accessed, so that it is possible to identify extensively animals outside easily with mobile equipment, and (5) it must be applied to a part of the animal that is easily accessible for process control and removal, and it may not damage valuable meat portions.

The key advantage of these approaches lies in their ability to encode different types of information (barcode symbologies can contain information relating to the product and its process history), and the relative ease with which the data can be read. Data can

thus be read in real-time, facilitating the use of electronic identifiers for monitoring animal movements (Loftus, 2005).

4.3.1 Electronic ear tag

One of the first segments of the identification industry to use RFID technology was the ear tag industry. In 1993, Allflex USA, Inc. first introduced electronic tags. A microchip and a coiled copper antenna are encapsulated in a small plastic ear tag. The main advantage over the electronic implants is its stationary, whereas implants can migrate throughout the animal's body. Opponents argue that ear tags are unreliable because of the potential to be lost from the animal's ear.

4.3.2 Injectable transponder

Transponders have been injected into cattle, veal, calves, sheep and goats in a variety of body locations (kneefold, armpit, forehead, ear, etc) (Klindtworth *et al.*, 1999). In all studies, breakage, loss or failure of transponders, migration of transponders and recovery of transponders after slaughter were key concerns. Proponents of injectable transponders can be divided into two main factions: those who support implantation in the base of the ear and those who support the axilla as the superior site for implantation. Klindtworth *et al.* (1999) give preference to the scutulum (*cartilago scutiformis*) for site of implantation due to both the low presence of nerves and veins – almost painless injection with only minor bleedings – and the secure mechanical protection of the transponder given the combination of fat and cartilage in the scutulum. In a study of 5907 ewes over a four-year period, Nehring *et al.* (1998) found the axilla to have the higher retention/reading success (97.8%) and lower migration (1.3%), compared to the base of the ear (92.8% retention/reading success; 6% migration).

4.3.3 Ruminant bolus

A microchip and antenna are placed inside a small glass ampoule held in a high specific gravity ceramic capsule (bolus) and inserted orally into the ruminant's fore-stomach, usually the reticulum. Caja *et al.* (1999) reported that zero porosity and atoxic ceramic material (alumina) of high specific weight (higher than 3.3 g/cc) was used to produce a bolus for enclosing different types of glass encapsulated transponders.

Two types of readers are used, either static or portable. The static readers would be located in facilities with a large throughput of livestock, such as livestock marts, abattoirs, feedlots or cattle export premises. The static reader would automatically read the RFID tag as the animal passed through the reading field. The electronic identification would be stored and downloaded into a database containing an information file relating to that animal. The portable reader would operate on farms where the electronic identity of the animal could be linked to a veterinary inspection or other management procedures (Fallon, 2001).

The electronic rumen bolus has some advantages over an injectable electronic implant in avoiding potential contamination of meat and by-products and in avoiding the loss of saleable meat as occurs with migration of injected transponders. The rumen bolus also offers a significantly higher level of security. Additional benefits to the use of rumen boluses are the lack of physical damage or pain to the animal which can occur after injection of transponders (McAllister *et al.*, 1998). In cattle, stress due to bolus insertion is minimal. However, an external electronic ear tag would be much easier to recover at slaughter compared to a rumen bolus. Additionally, Klindtworth *et al.* (1999) reported that, when hand-held readers are used, the reading of a bolus seems to be more difficult and time-consuming than reading of injectable transponders and electronic ear tags.

The main disadvantage of the rumen bolus is its cost. The heavy electronic rumen bolus is more expensive than either injectable transponder or the

electronic ear tag. In addition, the animal with the rumen bolus will require an external method of identification for routine management of the animals.

4.3.4 Main results of the IDEA Project

The IDEA project results show that the time spent to apply an electronic identifier to **cattle** varies between 3 to 10 minutes and is independent of the identifier used (Table 3). The tagging efficiency (number of animals tagged per day) depends on farm size, type of production system (intensive or extensive) and housing and restraining systems.

Table 3. Some important results from the IDEA project. Compiled from IDEA Final Report (2001)

Electronic identifier	Aspects	Buffalo	Cattle	Sheep	Goat
Ruminal Bolus	No. species/day ¹	50-60	50-120	300	300
	Tagging time (min) ²	4-10	3-10	>3	>3
	Reading failures (%) ³	0.35	0.28	0.28	0.23 ⁶
	Recovery at slaughter (%) ⁴	100	58	99.7	99.9
Ear tag	No. species/day	- ⁵	50-120	300	-
	Tagging time (min)	-	3-10	>3	-
	Reading failures (%)	-	2.32	0.37	-
	Recovery at slaughter (%)	-	93	100	-
Injectable	No. species/day	-	50-120	-	-
	Tagging time (min)	-	3-10	-	-
	Reading failures (%)	-	1.05	-	-
	Recovery at slaughter (%)	-	75	-	-

(1) Number of species that could be identified per day per tagging team

(2) Tagging time per animal

(3) The highest percentage of reading failures are shown

(4) The lowest percentage of electronic identifiers recovered at the slaughterhouse are shown

(5) No experiments were done

(6) This value does not take into account Spain's results

In global terms, the reading failures of the ruminal bolus in cattle remained rather constant with time, and in average, remained lower than 0.28% in the worst case. The reading failures of electronic ear tags showed instead a tendency to increase after 1 month after tagging with average failure of 0.63,

1.58 and 2.32% at 1, 7, and 14 months after tagging. The reading failures of the injectable transponder increased to 1% after tagging and decreased beyond this point. The recovery percentages in slaughterhouse varied depending on the tag type. Electronic ear tag and injectable identifiers showed the highest percentage of recovery.

The reading failure percentage of electronic ear tags applied to **sheep** showed a slight tendency to increase after one month after tagging with average failure of 0.16, 0.24 and 0.37% at 1, 7 and 14 months after tagging, respectively. In contrast, the observed reading failure of bolus in sheep remained rather constant with time, and in average, was lower than 0.28%. The recovery results for sheep did not present high differences between tag types (99.7% recovery for boluses and 100% for ear tags).

4.4 Biometric identifiers

Recent advances in the development of biometric technologies promise a non-invasive solution to individual animal identification. An animal biometric identifier has been defined by Shadduck and Golden (2002a) as any *measurable, robust, and distinctive* physical characteristic that can be used to identify or verify the claimed identity of an animal.

Measurable: the characteristic can be easily presented to a sensor and converted into a quantifiable, digital format.

Robustness: measure of the extent to which the characteristic is subject to significant changes over time.

Distinctive: measure of the variations of differences in the biometric patterns among the general population. The higher the degree of distinctiveness, the more unique the identifier.

The acceptance of any biometric identification system is based on reliability, ease of use, ease of implementation and cost (concepts are adapted for animal identification). The data should be computer-friendly and the system must easily link to post-slaughter identification systems.

Reliability: Sensor noise, limitations of the processing methods, and more importantly, variability in the biometric feature (iris, retina, muzzle prints) might contribute to an incorrect animal verification.

Ease of use and ease of implementation: To foster improvements and encourage widespread deployment, the biometric system needs to be made easily accessible for integration and implementation.

Cost: Even though the biometric identification systems have developed into a very cost effective solution, there are a number of issues to consider when estimating the total cost to deploy such a system. These issues involve equipment, installation, training costs, software and system maintenance and operation costs.

Biometric labelling systems incorporate biological data and cannot be easily faked, altered or appropriated. Technologies include retinal and iris imaging, nose printing and DNA profiling. In addition to being less prone to error or fraud, these labelling methods are permanent, covering the life history of the animal, and in the case of DNA the full product life history. However, one of the drawbacks of biometric identifiers is that they are typically non-visible and require specialised technology to read (Loftus, 2005).

Golden (2000) points out that eye-based biometric identification systems are low-cost and reliable and present an immediate advantage over RFID systems because there is no mass-produced equipment requirement. These types of identification do not require putting a foreign object into the animal or an ear tag. Thus, there is no possibility of transferring identity from one animal to another by removing the electronic chip and putting it into another animal (Dziuk, 2003). In addition, biometric identification would reduce the risk of substitution and establish confidence in the

transaction. Illegal killing, transporting, selling and buying of animals could be more easily controlled and monitored. Possibly the greatest impact of positive, unalterable and permanent identification will come as a result of lessening the opportunity for fraud and confusion (Dziuk, 2003). On the other hand, digital imaging equipment has become relatively inexpensive, which adds to their benefit.

4.4.1 Iris imaging

It is said that iris patterns are not well established in the very young animal (Dziuk, 2003), and that it is susceptible to change through a bovine animal's development. Additionally, Golden (2000) indicates that images of the iris can be difficult to acquire when corneal scarring occurs. In spite of these drawbacks, two methods for animal identification using iris pattern have been patented by Musgrave and Cambier (2002) and Suzaki (2001) (Iridian Technologies, Inc and Oki Electric Industries, respectively). In 1997, Oki Electric Industries set out a research on biometric identification system using iris images for racehorses in Japan. They developed a special camera, an iris coding algorithm, and code-matching software. However, due to the poor market demand, they never performed commercial trials (Ebara, 2005). Evans (2004) listed some issues that would make the iris-based identifier inappropriate for horses: (i) horse's iris pattern does not stabilise until several months of age, (ii) inability of horse to remain motionless for duration of scan, resulting in poor quality scans, (iii) horses do not have sufficient markers within the iris to identify unique pattern for each animal, and (iv) horse's pupil size varies significantly between contraction and dilation.

Musgrave and Cambier (2002) propose capturing an animal's eye image using an iris acquisition device that combines a camera, an optical system, an illumination source, and a viewing screen in a hand-held device. A biometric template is then extracted from the captured iris image. The identity of the animal is determined by comparing the obtained biometric template with a previously obtained and stored biometric template, collected under conditions which permit independent verification of identity, and stored in a database along with identification information. Susaki (2001) provides the algorithms

for outlining the pupil and irial granule in an input image of an eye of an animal to be identified. Then, an image of the irial granule is mapped into a polar coordinate system whose origin is the centre of the reference axis. The shape of the irial granule corrected in the above manner is compared with a reference shape stored in a memory to determine whether the input image arises from the same animal or not.

Although some attempts to develop an iris-based animal identification system were made, it is very unlikely that further advances could be done in the future, due to the following reasons (Daugman, 2005): (1) blood stock animals like cattle have deeply recessed irides, almost in the middle of their eyes, which have little texture or pattern structure, using either visible or near-infrared band imaging; and (2) the pupil is often dilated to 75% or more of the iris diameter, so little iris is visible in barn conditions. In outdoor conditions the constriction of the pupil is highly non-uniform, forming a long narrow slit for most prey herbivores. This exaggerated inhomogeneity of iris elasticity complicates the generation of IrisCodes that would be independent of papillary dilation.

4.4.2 Retina imaging

4.4.2.1 Anatomical bases of the retina

The retina ranges in thickness from about 100-500 μm . It is a composite of numerous cellular and synaptic layers which can be grossly split into an outer epithelial layer (referred to as the sensory retinal epithelium or retinal pigment epithelium) and an inner sensory layer (referred to as the sensory retina or neuroretina). The retina is one of the most metabolically active tissues in the body (Young, 1979). Its major function is to convert light energy into chemical and electrical energy so that vision can occur.

The order of retinal layers starting from outer to inner layers (that is, from choroids to vitreous) is as follows: retinal epithelium, photoreceptor outer

segments, photoreceptor inner segments, outer or external limiting membrane, outer or external nuclear layer, outer or external plexiform layer, inner nuclear layer, inner plexiform layer, ganglion cell layer, nerve fibre layer and internal limiting membrane. The ocular fundus is often described according to the type of vasculature found.

Holangiotic: the retinal blood supply (inner layers) is from central or cilioretinal arteries. This is seen in dogs, cats, cattle, goats, sheep, pigs, rats, mice, primates and others (Figure 8).

Merangiotic: only part of the inner retina is supplied by retinal vessels. This is the type present in the rabbit (Figure 9).

Paurangiotic: the retinal vessels are small and extend only a short distance from the optic disk so that only the inner retina immediately surrounding the disk is supplied; the rest of the retina is independent on the choriocapillaris. This is seen in the horse. The guinea pig (Figure 10) has vessels in the optic disk, and because the optical disk is composed of retinal ganglion cell axons, this could technically be considered retinal vasculature.

Anangiotic: no part of the retina contains vessels and therefore the entire retina is dependent upon the choriocapillaris. This is present in some rodents such as the degu. Birds also have anangiotic ocular fundi, but have a structure called the *pecten*, which arises in the region of the optic disk to protrude into the vitreous and may be important in providing inner retinal nourishment (Figure 11).

4.4.2.2 Normal fundus appearance for some species

a. Horse

A number of 60-70 small vessels (cannot differentiate arterioles from venules) arise from the border (Gelatt and Finocchio, 1970). Tapetal regions show some diffuse, but light melanosis. The optic disk is situated ventral to center

Figure 8. Holangiomatic ocular fundus (goat)

Figure 9. Merangiomatic ocular fundus (rabbit)

Figure 10. Paurangiotic ocular fundus (guinea pig)

Figure 11. Anangiotic ocular fundus (bird, screech owl)

and is non-myelinated, ellipsoid (long axis horizontal) and slightly depressed; the tapetum usually ends a short distance above it. Stars of Winslow are prominent (Figure 12).

b. Cow

Three major veins (very prominent) and three or more arterioles; the dorsal vein and arteriole often twist around each other. The tapetum is well developed. The optic disk is non-myelinated and horizontally oval or sometimes round, often with indistinct borders; the tapetum usually ends at or around the dorsal border. Stars of Winslow are prominent (Figure 13).

c. Sheep

Generally similar to cow's retina. The optic disk has a typical 'kidney bean' shape to it, with one half often appearing incomplete (Figure 14).

d. Goat

It presents several major veins with several arterioles. The tapetum is similar to cow's. The optic disk is non-myelinated and round; the tapetum often develops to surround it. Stars of Winslow are prominent (Figure 15).

e. Pig

It presents four major veins and several arterioles. The optic disk is non-myelinated and horizontally ellipsoid. No tapetum (Figure 16).

4.4.2.3 Congenital and acquired abnormalities of the retina

Because the retina, optic nerve and vitreous are closely related, abnormalities in one often are associated with abnormalities in the others.

a. Persistent hyaloid artery and remnants

Various degrees of persistence of hyaloid system may occur, usually without affecting the vision. There may be a short remnant attached to the lens or the optic disk. The remnant attached to the lens may hang down into the vitreous and have a coiled appearance; the remnant of the optic disk appears as a small

Figure 12. Normal fundus appearance of horse

Figure 13. Normal fundus appearance of cow

Figure 14. Normal fundus appearance of sheep

Figure 15. Normal fundus appearance of goat

Figure 16. Normal fundus appearance of pig

out-of-focus grey dot when viewed straight-on and may occur in cattle. However, most of these problems are not common and treatment is neither necessary nor practical.

b. Optic nerve hypoplasia

This is uncommon, but has been reported in cattle, horses, cats and dogs (Barr *et al.*, 1988). Affected eyes usually are blind or have very poor vision. It is not unusual to be unilateral in which case it is clinically silent; diagnosis in these cases usually is incidental.

c. Retinal dysplasia

This is a generalised abnormal development of the retina and can be manifest as benign appearing retina folds or more serious disorganisation of the entire retina with total separation of the sensory retina from the retinal epithelium. The serious form is also known as vitreoretinal dysplasia because the vitreous often is involved. In cattle, retinal dysplasia is seen as a part of multiple ocular anomaly syndrome, especially in shorthorns.

d. Bracken-induced retinal degeneration in sheep

This disease, also known as “bright blindness”, has been reported in the UK and is due to ingestion of bracken (*Pteris aquilina*) (Barnett *et al.*, 1972). The affected sheep show no signs other than progressive retinal degeneration which clinically is similar to that seen in other species.

e. Light-induced retinal degeneration

Ambient light, even at low intensities, can cause irreversible outer retinal degeneration in many species (Lanum, 1978). This phenomenon has been observed using various light sources in rats, mice, rabbits, goats, pigs, pigeons and primates (Buyukmihci, 1980).

f. Proliferative optic neuropathy in horses

Occasionally, white or grey masses are seen on or near the optic disk in middle-aged or older horses (Vestre *et al.*, 1982). They are vascularised and are sometimes multilobular. The cause is not known.

4.4.2.4 The ocular fundus as a biometric identifier

Dziuk (2003) and Shaddock and Golden (2002b) agree on the fact that retinal blood vessels patterns remain essentially unchanged in the normally developing bovine and porcine eye from birth to maturity (Figure 17). After slaughter, the retina pattern will not change if the animal has been dead for less than six hours. Also, injuries on the eye's cornea do not interfere with the ability to get an accurate retinal image (Dougherty, 1999). Golden (1998, 2000) indicates that retinal imaging is preferable to retinal scanning as a retinal image allows for a more powerful and flexible analysis of the retinal data.

An OptiReader™ device has been developed by Optibrand in 1998 by which retinal images are acquired through the pupil using a hand-held computer in combination with an ocular fundus infrared digital camera, requiring virtually no contact with the animal (Figure 18).

Figure 17. Retinal images of 9 individual cows showing the unique retinal vascular patterns

As each animal is stabilised in the chute, the operator will point the reader at the animal's eye, engage the trigger, and move the reader towards the eye. The operator can look at the viewing LCD screen on the reader to help position the reader at the pupil of the eye. When the trigger is pressed, the targeting algorithm is started, which looks for the retinal structure in the eye. When the structure is found, the green light on the camera is turned on and three to five adjacent images are presented to the operator via the LCD screen. The operator can now release the trigger. The reader will choose the image with the best characteristics, but the operator can override the selection if he feels that the images are not acceptable. If an image is accepted, the green light is turned off and the reader is ready for the next animal.

Each time an image is captured, the date, time and location of the OptiReader device are entered into the computer. All this information, plus any additional information the operator may wish to enter via an alphanumeric keypad or USB port (for a barcode reader, for example), are included in an encrypted electronic file which subsequently is transmitted to a central data bank.

Figure 18. OptiReader™ developed by OptiBrand

The images are stored as a greyscale JPEG file with the following information encrypted and stored in the comment field of the file: GPS (longitude, latitude, date and time), reader's serial number, location ID, ear tag number (optional) and operator's ID (optional) (Golden, 1998). The image, GPS data and other data are retrieved via a number of different queries, including a search for a match of a reference image in the database. When a retinal image is taken, a template of the main retinal veins is extracted and stored. Whenever a retinal image of the same animal is taken, the template matching algorithm will recognise the animal ID (linked to the previously stored retinal image) based on a matching score. Thus, the user should set a score threshold for the matching algorithm (Figure 19).

Because the identification is based on a unique marker, the match between the animal and its ID in the database is essentially perfect, thus preventing lost animals and fraud. The animal's ID can be linked to other identification systems such as (Shadduck and Golden, 2002b):

- lot and item bar coded numbers – for product trace back;
- specific owner identification – to assure accountability for animal disease or to record where and to whom an animal was sold;
- animal health and/or performance records, etc.

Figure 19. Image matching process of OptiReader system. Image templates are overlaid and a matching score (0-100) is produced. *Courtesy of Optibrand*

4.4.3 Muzzle pattern imaging

The muzzle pattern can be considered as a biometric identifier due to its uniqueness. The problems associated with nose printing using ink, as outlined in 4.2.5, can readily be overcome with the use of digital imaging (Figure 20). Minagawa *et al.* (2002) determined a square area for image analysis, based on the minimum length between the nostril borders of the sample (Figure 21). After applying techniques of filtering, binary transforming, thinning, and feature extraction, their technique was able to reach only 68% of correct animal identification. However, more robust pattern recognition techniques can lead to a successful matching method. Figure 22 shows examples of beef cattle nose prints where five consecutive points must be found between prints to determine a positive match (Blomeke *et al.*, 2004).

Figure 20. Digital image of muzzle pattern of cattle (Extracted from Minagawa *et al.*, 2002)

Figure 21. Image analysis area of muzzle pattern used by Minagawa *et al.* (2002)

Figure 22. Examples of beef cattle nose prints (Blomeke *et al.*, 2004)

4.4.4 DNA pattern

Each individual has a unique DNA pattern and a unique complement of antibodies that preclude tissue and organ transplants except in cases of identical twins or very highly inbred strains. These means would be most effective in tracing animal's heritage and for identifying products and parts with the advent of quick, simpler means of establishing a particular DNA or antibody pattern. The use of these techniques for positive, accurate, unalterable, quick and easy means of identification should greatly lessen errors in interpreting information arising from these animals.

During 2001 – 2003, a project on “Electronic identification and molecular markers for improving traceability of livestock and meat” (EID+DNA) was conducted in Spain. The EID provided a real time tagging and tracing-back method for on-farm use and administrative follow-up until slaughtering, and the DNA profile was the method used to audit the tracing-back of animals, carcasses and meat cuts throughout the meat chain. Biopsy-tagging (by using specially-designed ear tags) was an easy and tamper-proof system for sampling DNA in animals and carcasses. The storage of biopsies proved to be effective for analysis of DNA microsatellites and SNP in cattle, sheep and pig. Data from EID and DNA profiling was processed, coded and stored in a new

developed database provided with the necessary tools for data comparison and data retrieval (Caja *et al.*, 2004).

4.4.4.1 DNA identification techniques for live animals

A number of ways in which the DNA technology can be used for animal identification are described below (Cunningham and Meghen, 2001):

- Verification of identity by comparison of a query sample with a sample previously taken from the same animal. Biological samples are often taken from livestock for purposes of disease control and eradication. The availability of these samples provides a possible means of authenticating the current identity of an animal under scrutiny.
- Systematic sampling of young animals and archiving of samples. If samples are taken at first tagging/identification, this provides a very powerful control tool. For example, a hair or tissue sample taken for a calf and associated with its ear tag or electronic identification number and securely stored for the life of the animal will provide for the possibility of testing the animal and confirming that its conventional identity has not been altered in the period between first tagging and subsequent or secondary DNA sampling.
- Systematic sampling and DNA profiling of animals. Each of the source samples is to be tested and its information stored on a DNA database. This has the additional benefit of allowing positive identification of the tag number or electronic identification of an unmarked animal.

Cunningham and Meghen (2001) indicate that, for identification of live animals, universal use of DNA profiles would not be justified. However, universal archiving of tissue samples offers a powerful means of controlling the integrity of tag-based identification.

In 2003, Allflex Australia launched “DNA Tag”. This system combines a permanent visual or electronic ear tag with a DNA sample collector (Figure 23). The tags and the DNA sample collector are all preprinted with a unique code which matches them together. At the time when the tag is inserted, a sample of tail hair follicles is collected for dispatch to the laboratory. A computer database links the animal in the field with the archived DNA sample which can be used at any time for genetic testing or identification purposes. Even after the animal is killed, a sample of meat can be taken and traced back to the hair sample collected from the live animal.

Figure 23. DNATag and hair samples collector from Allflex, Australia

4.4.4.2 DNA identification techniques for meat products

In 1998, a system for meat traceability using DNA was first proposed by Meghen *et al.* (Cunningham and Meghen, 2001) and developed by IdentiGEN Ltd. (Ireland). The company’s pioneering “TraceBack” technology has been used by the Irish supermarket chain SuperQuinn since 1998 and provides full traceability for over 100 000 carcasses (Nugent, 2004). TraceBack calls for a DNA sample to be collected from a live animal or carcass before it is processed. The samples can be used later, if necessary, to verify the source of the meat delivered. The system includes a patented DNA sampling device for on-farm testing and a meat sampling device for the slaughter-house.

Figure 24 illustrates the TraceBack system. A biological tissue sample is taken from each animal / carcass at a point prior to the loss of the individual identity. This sample is identified with a code that links it to the individual animal identity and the sample can either be maintained in an archive for subsequent analysis (Fig. 24a), or analysed and the resultant DNA profiles stored in a database along with information on animal origins. If the sample is maintained in archive, the storage period can vary, but is typically a multiple of the normal recommended usable life of the meat product (Cunningham and Meghen, 2001). Storing samples or their associated DNA profiles does not in itself constitute a traceability system, rather it provides traceback capability, which could potentially be used to locate the source of a product should a particular need arise (Loftus, 2005).

Further samples are routinely taken from a defined proportion of meat derived from the source carcasses (Fig. 24b). A critical requirement is that, through batch identification, the system provides a link between the meat from which the derived meat samples have been taken and one or a number of source carcass samples (Fig. 24c). Source carcass samples and associated meat samples are processed through a DNA identification laboratory (Fig. 24d).

For each source and meat sample, an animal specific DNA profile is generated. Comparison between the sample DNA profiles is made (Fig. 24e). This comparison enables individual meat samples to be matched to an individual source carcass sample (Figure 25). Failure to identify a matching source carcass indicates that the meat product has been incorrectly labelled (Cunningham and Meghen, 2001).

Figure 24. Principles of DNA traceability. Sampling of carcasses (a) and meat (b), linked by batch number (c); generation of DNA profiles (d) and identification of animal of origin by comparison of meat profile with database batch of animal profiles (e). Extracted from Cunningham and Meghen (2001)

Figure 25. A typical image of a DNA test result. On the right-hand side is an actual gel image of five samples, one from a retail meat sample (lane 1) and four from carcasses (lane 2-5). The two sets of numbers labelled as Microsatellite 1 and Microsatellite 2 are the numerical interpretations of the dark bands that appear in the DNA gel image. Extracted from Cunningham and Meghen (2001)

This routine programme of verification sampling and DNA matching is being used in some European markets to continuously monitor the ability of a supply chain to provide traceable products. A similar system for meat traceability using DNA, “SureTRACK”, was developed by Alleflex Australia in 2000. This system, used extensively in USA and Japan, consists of a simple sample collection, the use of a secure archiving and storage system and DNA analysis. A DNA sample is taken from every beef carcass and stored to enable future traceability.

In Canada, the development and production of transgenic animals is increasing with advances in this technology. In particular, the transformation of livestock animals has become more prevalent and now includes sheep, cattle, goats and pigs. Numerous reports (Loftus, 2005) have indicated that public acceptance of animal biotechnology will be essential if it is to realise its potential. To gain such acceptance, a range of consumer concerns will need to be addressed through a transparent and trustworthy regulatory process. A component of this process will be the inclusion of mechanisms to ensure that if a particular problem arises, the affected animals and their by-products can quickly be tracked and traced. A study on DNA traceability conducted in Canada (Morris *et al.*, 2005) positively linked meat products sampled along the supply chain with source carcasses. This was carried out with a view of testing the efficacy of traceability from farm to slaughter, slaughter to boning hall and slaughter to supermarket. Traceability levels were found to be 100% from farm to slaughter, 97.5% from slaughter to boning, and 96.9% from slaughter to supermarket. The results showed the suitability of a DNA-based traceability tool to enhance the capacity to track and monitor transgenic animal stock that are considered high risk or that remain unapproved for food/feed use.

The principal limitation of the DNA technology is the inability to read the DNA code in real time, a key requirement for trace-forward applications and the monitoring of product movements (Loftus, 2005). However, it is expected that progress in DNA testing will come in two areas: current techniques will improve offering more automation, precision and faster processing times, and new techniques will be developed.

4.4.5 Immunological labelling

The bioactive labelling system “ImmunoTrack”, developed by Responsif GmbH, Germany (Gareis and Groschup, 1998; Raschke *et al.*, 2006), allows traceability of meat from beef cattle and pig by means of immunisation with highly antigenic L- or D- peptide sequences (10 to 20 amino acids in length) chemically conjugated to the carrier protein keyhole limpet hemocyanin (KLH). The single administration of or prime/boost immunisations with these peptide-KLH compounds in the presence of appropriate adjuvants induce strong peptide-specific antibody responses in pigs and cattle after a certain incubation period. By combination of multiple peptides, the origin (e.g. country, region, farm) and other characteristics (e.g. breed, organic farming) can be encoded.

In consequence, these anti-peptide-antibodies or label can be detected in the living animal’s blood (serum) as well as in the flesh (meat juice) after slaughtering and butchering. The label can be detected in the laboratory by a routine method known as the ELISA test (Enzyme Linked Immuno Sorbent Assay). Alternatively, a rapid on-site test can be used which delivers results in less than five minutes. It can be applied for the surveillance of all steps of meat production right to the end consumer.

In contrast to DNA technology, the ImmunoTrack system does not lead to the individual identification of the animals, but exclusively allows the tracking of livestock based on their appropriate allocation as, for example, regional meat producers, meat suppliers for trade chains or quality assurance systems for meat (Raschke *et al.*, 2006)

5. Research topics in animal biometrics

- From retinal images of same animals taken under various conditions (indoors, outdoors, different time intervals and different operators), the variability in image quality should be evaluated so as to establish an appropriate range of cut-off matching score for the pattern matching algorithm of the OptiReader device.
- Validation of retinal imaging technology for cattle and sheep by means of an experiment involving a large number of animals whose retinal patterns are imaged under different time intervals (i.e., birth, every month, before slaughter) and conditions (indoors, outdoors).
- Given the difficulty in obtaining ink muzzle prints, a way of acquiring digital images depicting defined ridge patterns of muzzle would be of interest. The use of indirect oblique illumination or stereo imaging could be evaluated. With good quality muzzle images, robust algorithms for image processing and feature extraction can be investigated.
- DNA matching tests could be performed in order to confirm accuracy of biometric-based traceback system. Hair samples of livestock can be taken on farm and stored. Meat samples originated from sampled animals can be taken randomly at slaughterhouse, processing stage or distribution level. In fact, this audit method is being practised in Japan (Smith *et al.*, 2005).
- Due to the vessels arrangement of porcine retina, the OptiReader's matching algorithm is not expected to succeed with this type of images. Another algorithm that accounts for the differences encountered in porcine retinal images should be developed.
- The feasibility of embedding a biometric identifier (i.e., a binary template of retinal vessels) in matrix barcodes or 2D barcodes (Noore *et al.*, 2004) should be evaluated.

6. Conclusions

A unique and tamper-proof animal identifier is the core of an effective livestock traceability system. In contrast to traditional animal identification systems (plastic eartags, bar coded eartags, tattoos, hot and freeze branding, etc), biometric identifiers incorporate biological data and cannot be easily faked or altered. The main advantage of the biometric identifiers over the electronic identifiers is the absence of any attached device. Although RFID-based identifiers are currently the most popular solutions for animal identification, their main drawbacks are still the cost (especially for boluses), the possibility of loss (electronic ear tags), the possibility of migration and infection (for injectable transponders), and recovery after slaughter.

To date animal biometric-based identifiers comprise retina imaging, iris imaging, muzzle printing, DNA profiling and immunological labelling. In addition to being less prone to error or fraud, these biometric identifiers are permanent, covering the life history of the animal (retina, iris and muzzle patterns), and in the case of DNA and antibodies the full product life history. Major difficulties arise when carcasses are disassembled into component parts prior to retail packaging. In this case, the DNA and immunological labelling technologies present additional advantages over retina, iris and muzzle patterns technology. However, the principal limitation of the DNA technology is the inability to read the DNA code in real time, a key requirement for tracing applications and the monitoring of product movements.

Contrary to its human counterpart, iris pattern has not yet proven to be a permanent animal identification method due to anatomical reasons and its susceptibility to environmental damage. Even though muzzle pattern has proven to be unique to each animal, it has not been further studied in terms of digital image acquisition to replace ink printing, image feature extraction and automated matching algorithms. To date, the retinal-based traceability system, developed by OptiBrand, appears to be the most robust, tamper-proof and non-invasive biometric method.

The challenge of meat traceability at all production stages (abattoir, boning halls, processors, etc), already studied by GS1 Ireland and industrial partners based on

barcode technology (Anonymous, 2005b), should serve as a basis for further investigations on the use of RFIDs in the supply chain management.

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